

CYBERLENINKA

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SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Ergasheva Guli Buranovna

THE WAYS TO REFLECT AFFECTIVE EMOTIONS (ANGER, JOY, HORROR,
ADMIRATION) AND THEIR EXPRESSION IN LITERARY TEXTS

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